

ILLOCUTIONARY SPEECH ACTS IN THE DISCOURSE OF MEDICAL ADVERTISEMENTS

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Abstract. Speech acts serve as a means of achieving the goal that communicators set out to communicate. In this article, the issue of illocutionary speech act is covered by the example of medical advertisements.

Key words: medical advertisement, speech act, communicative intention, illocution.

Illocution is a concept related to communicative intention (goal). Pragmalinguists have their own approaches to grouping types of speech acts. In particular, J. Austin offers such types of illocutionary speech act as verdictive, exercisive, comissive, non-habitual, expository. J. Searle justifies the types of illocutionary act in communication, such as assertive, directive, commissive, declarative and expressive. J. Leach, the author of the treatise "Pragmalinguistics", distinguishes the groups of speech acts based on "sociolinguistic indicators and how they are related to the purpose of ensuring politeness in the communication process and establishing this environment" competitive, convivial, collaborative, conflictive divides into groups such as [1, 62]. According to A. Depperman, J. Austin's approach is bottom-up and reveals the possibility that speech acts differ between societies (cultures). Below, we will try to analyze illocutionary speech acts in medical advertisements based on J. Austin's classification.

Verdictive speech act. Such speech acts represent the content of judgment and command. Such an act is also observed in medical advertisements:

... *Pain, pain, pain! Stop! There is Tempalgin.* (From the advertising text of the drug "Tempalgin")

Stop diarrhea, Stopdiar! (From the advertising text of the drug "Stopdiar").

Exercisive speech act. It means forcing, advising, and warning by using one's authority. We observe: - **You can't! - You can't!** (From the text of the "Magne B6" advertisement)

Try supporting Creon! (From the advertising text of the drug "Creon")

Commissive speech act. In the content of such a speech act, promises are expressed, as well as various obligations. In medical advertisements, the commissive speech act is skillfully used: **I want, I can, I will!** (From the advertising text of the drug "Teraflex")

Behavioral speech act. Speech acts that have the meaning of behaving in a group, reacting to someone's behavior are often used in medical advertisements. For example:

(The sick boy coughs incessantly).

Neighbor woman: - Peace? After all, there is a tried and tested tool!

Bromhexine Berlin-Chemi is an active ingredient in Namyotal. It helps to dilute the sputum and expel it from the lungs.

*Young man: - **The tool you gave me is useful.** (Thank you).* (From the advertising text of the drug "Bromhexin Berlin-Hemi")

Expository speech act. The peculiarity of such a speech act is that it occurs in the process of the speaker explaining, confirming and explaining his opinion in the process of communication [1, 63]:

Mother: - Our kitchen has the best dishes!

Girl: - The Japanese are balanced. Everything is delicious.

Mother: - We need modern, proven medicine! (From the advertising text of the drug "Mezim").

So, according to the observations based on J. Austin's classification, there are various forms of illocutionary act in medical advertisements, among which exercisive speech act is relatively actively used.

References:

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